

JOURNAL OF TECHNOLOGY ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND RURAL DEVELOPMENT

Labour - Management Relations: The Challenges of Enduring Industrial Relations in Nigeria -Dr. Felix A. Onabajo	Page 1
Approaches To Rural Development In Nigeria - Prof. S.A. Olateru-Olagbegi	Page 10
.Effectiveness Of Training And Development In Enhancing Productivity In Incorporate Organisations - Adebayo T.F.	Page 18
Culture And Interpersonal Interaction Of An Adolescent. - Dr. Deji Olesin	Page 30
The Challenges And Prospects Of Information Technology On Banking Industry In 21st Century In Nigeria - Prof. Adeyemo Kabiru Aderemi	Page 37
Mass Incommunication As A Persistent Problem Of Development Communication In Nigeria - Nureni Aderemi Adeniran, Ph.d	Page 47
Industrial Risk Management - Dr. Felix A. Onabajo	Page 57

Journal of Technology, Entrepreneurship and Rural Development
Vol. 1 No 3 September 2007

Chairman, Editorial Board
PROF. OLUJIMI FATUROTI

Dept. Of Fisheries Management University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria.

Editor in Chief
PROFESSOR KEN ATTUFUAH

*Ghana Institute for Management and Public Administration
University of Ghana LEGON*

ENGINEER JAMES ALIU

Executive Director

Ghana Institute of Certified Public administrators TEMA

COL. ADEMOLA OLANREWaju

National War College, Abuja.

THE POLICY MAKERS' JOURNAL: 'AN INSIGHT'

JOURNAL OF TECHNOLOGY, ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND RURAL DEVELOPMENT
(J-TERD) ISSN 1119-8990) provides up-to-date materials on all aspects of Technology Entrepreneurship and Rural Development. This highly regarded and well researched journal contains papers based on world-wide research and practice relating to technology Entrepreneurship and Rural Development in systems and services of all kinds.

All contributions present the highest quality of research, and prior to publications are referred by an eminent editorial board and other distinguished experts.

Most of the review articles offer excellent in-depth analyses of timely topics. This journal is an essential reading for anyone involved in the management of Technology, Entrepreneurship and Rural Development.

The Journal speaks authoritatively and lobbies on all aspects of these subjects as they become important in social, economic and political milieu. The journal essentially carry book reviews occasionally as well as advertisements to support subscribers in the pursuit for their professional duties within their organisations.

Finally, J.TERD) Specialises in disseminating factual, and authoritative information on innovations, Research and Development, Information Technology, Pollution, Village Technology, including Rural poverty, Alleviation and Health Services.

TABLE OF CONTENT

<u>SN</u>	<u>TITLE</u>	<u>PAGE</u>
1.	Labour - Management Relations: The Challenges of Enduring Industrial Relations in Nigeria -Dr. Felix A. Onabajo	1
2.	Approaches To Rural Development In Nigeria - Prof. S.A. Olateru-olagbegi	10
3.	Effectiveness Of Training And Development In Enhancing Productivity In Incorporate Organisations - Adebayo T.F.	18
4.	Culture And Interpersonal Interaction Of An Adolescent. - Dr. Deji Olesin	30
5.	The Challenges And Prospects Of Information Technology On Banking Industry In 21st Century In Nigeria - Prof. Adeyemo Kabiru Aderemi	37
6.	Mass Incommunication As A Persistent Problem Of Development Communication In Nigeria - Nureni Aderemi Adeniran, Ph.d	47
7.	Industrial Risk Management - Dr. Felix A. Onabajo	57

THE CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY ON
BANKING INDUSTRY IN 21 ST CENTURY IN NIGERIA

PROF. ADEYEMO KABIRU ADEREMI

Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

As we move into the 21st century, banks all over the world realize that only those that overhaul the whole of their payment and service delivery and operations are likely to survive and prosper in the new millennium. This is due to the pressure of globalization, consolidation, deregulation and rapidly changing technology. In order to properly place themselves in favorable positions for competition and be one of the corporations to be reckoned with in the new century, banks are making use of information Technology (IT). In other words, paper-based transactions are being replaced by electronics-based transactions. Whether a bank will be successful or not depends on the extent to which it is investing on I.T and using I.T in an innovative manner. The reason for this is fact that in the future, banking transactions would be conducted in cyberspace. IT incorporates two main technologies or domains of study, namely computers and telecommunications, it is the technology of gathering, manipulating, storing and telecommunicating data. Today, the word data encompasses voice, text, number, fax graphics, pictures videos and multimedia. We shall first look at computers and telecommunication. This introductory aspect explains the nature of computers and telecommunications and how they come together to form what is called IT.

It looks at the future of the computers and IT generally. It also explains how computers can change the work place and some of the effects on or implications to the banking industry in particular.

Since the arrival of the Bank of England in 1694, the banking industry has not had another singular event that would revolutionize the industry as much as IT has. The arrival of IT is now taking banking away from good old neighborhood or high street branches to the cyberspace.

This is a major paradigm shift. This paper takes the focus of the previous paragraph a little further by examining the daunting problems posed by Nigeria's inadequate and inefficient telecommunications infrastructure to the banking industry in the country. It highlights the major

challenges facing the industry and proffers some suggestions on how they may be effectively tackled.

THE NATURE AND SCOPE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

IT refers to the new technology of gathering, storing, manipulating and transferring information. The heart of the technology lies on two major branches of technology, namely: computing and telecommunications. It is believed that IT is responsible for ushering in the post-industrial's era which, we are told is already with us (Toffler, 1983 and 1990; Bell, 1974; Forester, 1987; and Wohrem 1993). The first electronic information processor, a computer called the ENIAC, was invented in 1945 at the University of Pennsylvania. It was used for calculating ballistic tables for artillery and mortar fire during the Second World War. Since then, the world has seen many different types of computers first were the mainframes, then mini-computers, and then the ubiquitous personal computer (PCs). Today there are also notebook and palmtop computers.

We have moved from the mainframe-centric paradigm of computing to a network-centric one. The latter paradigm came about as a result of the increasingly widespread use of the PCS which were first used as standalone systems for personal, home, or office use. Today, more and more PCS are being interconnected to form networks. The LAN and the WAN.

They allow two or more computers to be linked together so that they can communicate data and information over short (LAN) or long (WAN) distances.

The communication is usually in the form of sending and receiving data files and electronics-mails (e-mail). It is also possible to use a computer to remotely log into another computer. Using e-mails, a person at home or in the office can send or receive messages from friends of business colleagues all over the world. There is also the worldwide network of all TCP/IP protocol-supported network nodes, called the Internet. The Internet comprises a number of interconnected local LANs, WANs and regional networks, varying in size from network within a single city to span continents. Around the world, many information providers are network that connected to the network which make up the internet. Apart from the telephone network the internet offers seamless and open communications in the area of mail, file transfers, long distance computing and discussion groups among others uses.

All over the world, information technology (IT) has become the digital nervous system of banks. This is because the business of banking is no longer perceived as merely the generation of deposit liabilities and creation of liquid assets; but rather the generation, storage, manipulation, communication of financial information. IT is perceived as an instrument for engendering competitive advantage in enterprises to develop more effective and efficient operational and management processes as pointed out by Frenzel (1996). It is also reason why Holoway (1995) writes that:

"An increasing important component of bank's technological focus is the personal computer. From risk management to commercial and consumer-lending and from employee training to product development and delivery, personal computers are being used as a tool to engineer the bank. In many instances, local area network (LANs) and wide area networks (WANs) are facilitating the process, enabling bank employees to access and use information in a more timely and efficient fashion".

The first Direct Bank in the U.K. Provides comprehensive service to about 900,000 customers with just staff strength of less than two dozens. This feat is achieved through the use of IT. It shows that banks today can operate in a more effective and efficient manner, with a lean number of staff, through the aid of modern technology. IT is now used to automate most of the processes in the banking industry of the more developed parts of the world; to drive delivery processes; and encapsulate many banking products.

Technology in banking has proven to be one of the major success stories of this century, as technologies such as automatic teller machines (ATMs) system, LANs and WANs, credit cards, electronic document interchange (EDI) systems, imaging systems, integrated banking systems, and client information filling (CIF) systems are now being routinely used by many banks to ensure a more efficient and effective operation and delivery of their product and services to customers. From all indications, the application of IT in all banking operation will intensify and spread in the 21st century. Information Technology has already become the nervous system of banks the world over. As we move into the new millennium, Nigerian banks will become uncompetitive if they do not have the means to deliver their banking services online and in real-time across all their branches within the country and abroad; if they do not have the backbone telecommunications infrastructure in the form of broad-band local and wider area networks; if they are not able to communicate and trade globally with the rest of the world through the cyberspace; and if they do not invest comprehensively in IT and the training of

their IT personnel. Nigerian banks since the 1980s, have generally performed very well in their investment profile and use of IT systems, compared to the rest of the industrial sector of the country (Woherem, 1997).

However, a lot still needs to be done if the sector is to catch up with the rest of the world be relevant in the globalized banking playing field of the 21st Century.

At the heart of this view epoch of economic and technological development is Information Technology (IT). The world as we know it is chop and donati als intes due f the wides read and increasing use of IT. The technology will engender what Toffler (1990) refers to as a 'power shift giving rise to an entirely new 'system for wealth creation' and the distribution of power. Accordingly to Frenzel (1996) writes that:

Information Technology (IT) is radically altering the balance of power between institutions, governments, and people by broadly disseminating important information. Power bases dependent on information are being built, transferred, and destroyed as critical information virtually flows around the globe without restriction.

Information technology has altered the way many people do their jobs, and has changed the nature of work in industrialized nations: The Practice of management has been greatly affected, and aspiring managers must be fluent in view management trends and techniques in order to succeed.

Writers like Toffler (1990), Glastonbury and LaMendola (1992), Frenzel (1996), Naisbit (1994), and Gates (1995), are also of the opinion that, in this millennium, IT would determine the countries that would be leaders and those that would be laggards; those that would be rich and those that would be powerful as against those that would be weak.

Countries that cannot trade using IT would be relegated to the periphery of world commerce and international relations. They would thus become the outcasts of the new world system. Equally, companies that do not have an appropriate IT infrastructure and the promotion of IT use in their operations, management and communication processes would also suffer an existential debacle in the business arena of the new era.

As we explained ealier, Information Technology comprises computing and telecommunications technologies. It is the merging of the two technologies, especially their organization and management aspects that. help in fashioning IT for organizational use (Woherem, 1991 and 1993;

Frenzel, 1996). In the 1970s and 1980s; the focus of IT was on its computing component. In fact, the computer was synonymous with IT revolution. Today, the focus is shifting quickly to telecommunications.

Now, when commentators write or speak about I, they are, invariably, referring to telecommunications and the information superhighway, of which telecommunication is a primary enabling technology. A lot has already been written elsewhere by the author on the computing part of IT and Africans see, for example Wherem 1991, 1992a, 1992b, 1993 and 1995). This write-up concentrates on telecommunications: the state of telecommunications in Africa and what African must do 'to embrace this technology as the evidence is overwhelming that wealth-creation in the 21st century will depend heavily on instant communication and dissemination of data, information, knowledge, ideas and symbols.

During the Industrial Revolution, Machinery drove change. From all available evidence, information, through the medium of telecommunications, will be the driving force in the present millennium.

PROBLEMS OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN NIGERIA BANKS

In Nigeria, the use of computers has been more widespread in banks than in all the other sectors of economy, except, perhaps, the energy sector.

Yet the banks still have along way to go in order to meet the standards of computer and telecommunication use in the banks in other part of the world. There are many problems confronting banks in Nigeria in their use of IT. Studies have revealed that most of the problems of the banks are telecommunications-related, and are directly traceable to problems with the public telephone network and service which are the backbone of the communications links and which depend on the service of the national public telecommunication operator, the Nigerian Telecommunication.

We have identified nine major categories of IT - related problems facing the banking industry in Nigeria today. Such problems include:

- **Lack of Investment Capital:** Funds that can be used to buy new information technologies and for modernizing existing system are general in short supply.

- **Systems Downtimes:** These are a chronic feature of Nigeria's telecommunications infrastructure. This is as a result of inconsistent power supply.
- Lack of knowledge of how to develop IT system internally
- Lack of internal maintenance skills or culture.
- Lack of IT knowledge
- The absence of IT Strategies
- Lack of basic infrastructure and facilities for the Exchange of information.
- Lac of maintenance culture in Nigeria Public Network
- Unhelpful government action

CHALLENGES AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Finding solutions to the problem outlined above would naturally task the ingenuity of Nigeria banks and the Nigeria government. However, some of the major challenges facing Nigerian banks in their attempt to ensure a smooth exchange of electronic data and information are as follow:

- The need to build a better and more optimal infrastructure that will serve as a backbone for communications within the banks;
- The need for banks to come together or collaborate in sourcing of common technologies such as VSAT, and to decide common standards for credit and electronic card;
- The need to professionalize IT system development, use and management in Nigerian banks;
- The need to improve the present telecommunications infrastructure
- The need to establish independent and private radio and satellite network. Having outlined the major communication problem and attendant challenges facing the banking industry in Nigeria. We now go on to look at ways to improve on the communication service being provided at macro-level. The problems and ensuing challenges have been with us for a long time; now plans are already in the works to implement all the outlined

solutions. These will no doubt improve the present state of the public network which constitutes the spine of telecommunication in the banking industry in Nigeria.

Some of the more practicable solutions that have been recommended as ways of moving the banking industry forward with regards to their communication problems and challenges are outlined below:

- Government should be sensitized about the need to formulate policies that would allow for long-term investment in the telecommunication industry.
- Emphasize should be placed on the importance of maintaining existing infrastructure and equipment;
- A reduction in import duties, tax and the time it takes IT equipment to be cleared at the customs post.
- The awareness of the banks, and indeed the general public, on the advantages of IT and communication should be increased by way of enlightenment campaigns and through any other productive means.

CONCLUSION

Computer and telecommunications have become very important as delivery systems and productivity tools of electronic data and information.

Nigerian banks have now realized that banking today requires prompt delivery of services, efficiency and the ability of customers to be served in any of their branches in the part of the country, without any encumbrances.

As a result of these banks embarked on the use of integrated banking applications that can help them to provide efficient, compressive and nation-wide services to their customers, through the use of WANs, with the acquisition of the above systems, they sold their promises of delivering online, real-time services. However, they have been finding out that their systems are down for about 5% of the time. Therefore, the single most important problem hindering Nigerian banks from providing international class banking services is the poor state of the country's telecommunications infrastructure.

REFERENCES

- Bell, D. 1974. *The coming of post-industrial society*. Heinemann, London
- Ejo-Orusa, H.A. 1997 *Development Myopia-Technology and the wealth of Nations. The Nigerian tragedy*. Zipidi press, Port Harcourt.
- Forester, T. 1987. *High-Tech Society*. Basil Blackwell Oxford.
- Frenzel C.W. 1996 *Management of Information Technology*. Boyd & Fraser Publishing Company Massachusetts, USA.
- Frenzel, F.W. 1996. *Management of Information Technology*. Boyd & Fraser Publishing Co Mssachusetts
- Gate, B. 1995. *The Road Ahead*. Viking Pengium, London
- Glastonbury, B. And W.
- Holloway, K.K. 1995. Using computers to branch out, *Marketing, March*, pp. 57-62.
- Lamendola 1992 *the integrity of Intelligence: A bill of right for the formation age*. St. Martin's Press, London
- Naibitt, J 1994. *Global paradox: The bigger the world economy, the more powerful its smallest player*. Nicholas Brealey Publishing, London
- Paul, M.C. Et al. 1993. *Capability Maturity Model for Software Version 1.1*, Technical Report, CMU/SEI-93-TR-24, SEI, Pennsylvania, USA.
- Ras-Work, T. 1995. *Telecommunications and the New World Economic order. The imperatives for the regional and global integration of Africa*. In: *Going for Growth in Nigerian Telecoms*. Pulse Marketing Communications Limited, Lagos
- Tartan, p. 1994.
- Opening address at the Africa Telecom '94 Cairo, Egypt, April 26
- Toffler, A. (1983). *The Third Wave* William Collins, London.
- Toffler, A 1990. *Power Shift*. Bantam Books, New York.
- Web, p. 1993. *The application of ISO 9000 to software development*, Proceeding of Wherem, E.E. (1991). *Information Technology and Africa, An appraisal of the present situation and future potential*. ProjectAppraisal, 6(1) 33-45.
- Wherem, E.E. (1992) *An information Technology Manpower Development strategy at Organizational Level"*.. In *information Technology Manpower Key issues for developing countries*. Bhatnagar, S.C. (Ed.) Tata McGraw-Ho; Publishing Company, New Delhi. India.

Wherem, E.E. (1992) Strategies of Indigenization of IT in Africa. Paper presented at the IFIP International Conference on the social Implications of Computers in Developing Countries, Nairobi, March 23-25.

Wherem, E.E. (1993). "Information Technology in Africa in Africa" Challenges and potentials ACTS Press Nairobi, Kenya; and RIKS, The Netherlands.

Wherem E.E. (1995) Towards a culture of management of software systems maintenance in Africa" In information Technology for Development Journal, IOS press, 6:5-14 Zorckozzy. P. 1982. Information Technology: An introduction. Pitman Publishing, London.

Wherem E.E. (2000) Information Technology in the Nigeria Banking Industry, Spectrum books Limited, Ibadan, Nigeria.